

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 106

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 106

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 106:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! Oh ^agive thanks to the LORD, for He ^bis good; For ^cHis lovingkindness is everlasting. ² Who can speak of the ^amighty deeds of the LORD, Or can show forth all His praise? ³ How blessed are those who keep ¹justice, ²Who ^apractice righteousness at all times!</p>	<p>Psa. 106:1 הַלְלוּ־יָהּ הוֹדוּ לַיהוָה כִּי־טוֹב כִּי לְעוֹלָם חַסְדּוֹ : ² מִי יִמְלֹל גְּבוּרֹת יְהוָה יִשְׁמַע כָּל־תְּהִלָּתוֹ : ³ אֲשֶׁר־יִשְׁמְרֵי מִשְׁפַּט עֲשֵׂה צְדָקָה בְּכָל־עֵת : ⁴ זָכַרְנִי יְהוָה בְּרָצוֹן עֲמָךְ פָּקֹדֵנִי בִישׁוּעָתְךָ : ⁵ לְרֵאוֹת בְּטוֹבַת בְּחִירֶיךָ לְשִׁמְחַת בְּשִׂמְחַת גּוֹיֶיךָ לְהִתְהַלֵּל עִם־נַחֲלָתְךָ : ⁶</p>
<p>Psa. 106:4 Remember me, O LORD, in ^{Your} ^afavor ¹toward Your people; Visit me with Your salvation, ⁵ That I may see the ^aprosperity of Your chosen ones, That I may ^brejoice in the gladness of Your nation, That I may ^cglory with Your ¹inheritance.</p>	<p>חָטְאֵנוּ עִם־אֲבוֹתֵינוּ הִעֲרִינוּ הַרְשָׁעֵנוּ : ⁷ אֲבוֹתֵינוּ בְּמִצְרַיִם לֹא־הִשְׁכִּילוּ נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ לֹא זָכְרוּ אֶת־רֹב חַסְדֶיךָ וַיִּמְרוּ עַל־יַם בְּיַם־סוּף : ⁸ וַיִּזְשִׁיעֵם לְמַעַן שְׁמוֹ לְהוֹדִיעַ אֶת־גְּבוּרָתוֹ : ⁹ וַיַּגְעֵר בְּיַם־סוּף וַיִּחַרֵב וַיּוֹלִיכֵם בְּתַהֲמוֹת כַּמָּדְבָר : ¹⁰ וַיִּזְשִׁיעֵם מִיַּד שׁוֹנֵא וַיַּגְאֵלֵם מִיַּד אוֹיֵב : ¹¹ וַיַּכְסּוּ־מַיִם צָרִיחַם אַחַד מֵהֶם לֹא נוֹתֵר : ¹² וַיַּאֲמִינוּ בְּדַבְרֵי יִשְׁרָאוֹל תְּהִלָּתוֹ : ¹³ מִהָרָו שָׁכַחוּ מַעֲשָׂיו לֹא־חִזְּרוּ לַעֲצָתוֹ : ¹⁴ וַיִּתְאַוּ תַּאֲוָה בַּמָּדְבָר וַיִּנְסוּ־אֵל בִּישִׁימוֹן : ¹⁵ וַיִּתֵּן לָהֶם שְׂאֵלָתָם וַיִּשְׁלַח רָזוֹן בְּנַפְשָׁם : ¹⁶ וַיִּקְנְאוּ לַמִּשֶׁה בַּמִּתְנַהֵּל לְאַחֲרָיו</p>
<p>Psa. 106:6 ^aWe have sinned ^{1b}like our fathers, We have committed iniquity, we have behaved wickedly. ⁷ Our fathers in Egypt did not understand Your ¹wonders; They ^adid not remember ²Your abundant kindnesses, But ^brebelled by the sea, at the ³Red Sea. ⁸ Nevertheless He saved them ^afor the sake of His name,</p>	<p>וַיִּזְשִׁיעֵם מִיַּד שׁוֹנֵא וַיַּגְאֵלֵם מִיַּד אוֹיֵב : ¹¹ וַיַּכְסּוּ־מַיִם צָרִיחַם אַחַד מֵהֶם לֹא נוֹתֵר : ¹² וַיַּאֲמִינוּ בְּדַבְרֵי יִשְׁרָאוֹל תְּהִלָּתוֹ : ¹³ מִהָרָו שָׁכַחוּ מַעֲשָׂיו לֹא־חִזְּרוּ לַעֲצָתוֹ : ¹⁴ וַיִּתְאַוּ תַּאֲוָה בַּמָּדְבָר וַיִּנְסוּ־אֵל בִּישִׁימוֹן : ¹⁵ וַיִּתֵּן לָהֶם שְׂאֵלָתָם וַיִּשְׁלַח רָזוֹן בְּנַפְשָׁם : ¹⁶ וַיִּקְנְאוּ לַמִּשֶׁה בַּמִּתְנַהֵּל לְאַחֲרָיו</p>

That He might ^bmake His power known.

⁹ Thus He ^arebuked the ¹Red Sea and it ^bdried up,

And He ^led them through the deeps, as through the wilderness.

¹⁰ So He ^asaved them from the ¹hand of the one who hated *them*,

And ^bredeemed them from the ¹hand of the enemy.

¹¹ ^aThe waters covered their adversaries;

Not one of them was left.

¹² Then they ^abelieved His words;

They ^bsang His praise.

Psa. 106:13 They quickly ^aforgot His works;

They ^bdid not wait for His counsel,

¹⁴ But ^acraved intensely in the wilderness,

And ^{1b}tempted God in the desert.

¹⁵ So He ^agave them their request,

But ^bsent a ¹wasting disease among them.

Psa. 106:16 When they became ^aenvious of Moses in the camp,

And of Aaron, the holy one of the LORD,

¹⁷ The ^aearth opened and swallowed up Dathan,

And engulfed the ¹company of Abiram.

¹⁸ And a ^afire blazed up in their ¹company;

The flame consumed the wicked.

Psa. 106:19 They ^amade a calf in Horeb

And worshiped a molten image.

קָדוֹשׁ יְהוָה : 17 תִּפְתַּח-אָרֶץ
וּתְבַלֵּעַ דָּתָן וְאֶת-כָּס עַל-עֵדֶת

אֲבִירָם : 18 וּתְבַעַר-אֵשׁ בְּעֵדֶתָם

לְהַכֹּה תְּלַהֲט רִשְׁעִים : 19 יַעֲשׂוּ-

עֵגֹל בְּחָרֵב וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְמִסְכָּה : 20

וַיִּמְרֹדוּ אֶת-כְּבוֹדָם בְּתִבְנִית שׂוֹר

אֲכָל עֹשֵׁב : 21 שָׁכְחוּ אֵל מוֹשִׁיעֵם

עֲשֵׂה גְדֻלוֹת בְּמִצְרַיִם : 22 גִּפְלֹאוֹת

בְּאֶרֶץ חָם נוֹרְאוֹת עַל-יַם-סוּף : 23

וַיֹּאמֶר לְהַשְׁמִידָם לוֹלֵי מִנְּשָׁה

בְּחִירוֹ עָמַד בַּפָּרֶץ לְפָנָיו לְהַשִּׁיב

חֲמָתוֹ מִהַשְׁחִית : 24 וַיִּמְאַסוּ בְּאֶרֶץ

חֲמָדָה לֹא-הֵאֱמִינוּ לְדַבְּרוֹ : 25

וַיִּרְגְּנוּ בְּאֵהָלֵיהֶם לֹא שָׁמְעוּ בְּקוֹל

יְהוָה : 26 וַיִּשְׂא יָדוֹ לָהֶם לְהַפִּיל

אֹתָם בְּמִדְבָּר : 27 וּלְהַפִּיל זֶרְעֵם

בְּגוֹיִם וּלְזֹרוֹתָם בְּאֶרְצוֹת : 28

וַיִּצְמְדוּ לְבַעַל פְּעוֹר וַיֹּאכְלוּ זִבְחֵי

מִתִּים : 29 וַיִּכְעִסוּ בְּמַעַלְלֵיהֶם

וּתְפָרֶץ-בָּם מַגִּפָּה : 30 וַיַּעֲמַד

פִּינֹחַס וַיִּפְלֹל וְתַעֲזַר הַמַּגִּפָּה : 31

וּתְתַשֵּׁב לוֹ לְצַדִּיקָה לְדָר וְדָר עַד-

עוֹלָם : 32 וַיִּקְצִיפוּ עַל-מִי מְרִיבָה

וַיִּרְע לְמִנְּשָׁה בְּעִבּוֹרָם : 33 כִּי-הִמְרֹדוּ

אֶת-רוּחֹו וַיִּבְטֹא בְּשִׁפְתָיו : 34 לֹא-

הִשְׁמִידוּ אֶת-הָעַמִּים אֲשֶׁר אָמַר

יְהוָה לָהֶם : 35 וַיִּתְעַרְבוּ בְּגוֹיִם

וַיִּלְמְדוּ מַעֲשֵׂיהֶם : 36 וַיַּעֲבְדוּ אֶת-

20 Thus they ^aexchanged their glory
 For the image of an ox that eats
 grass.

21 They ^aforgot God their Savior,
 Who had done ^bgreat things in
 Egypt,

22 ^{1a}Wonders in the land of Ham
 And awesome things by the ²Red
 Sea.

23 Therefore ^aHe said that He would
 destroy them,
 Had not ^bMoses His chosen one
 stood in the breach before Him,
 To turn away His wrath from
 destroying *them*.

24 Then they ^adespised the ^bpleasant
 land;
 They ^cdid not believe in His word,
 25 But ^agrumbled in their tents;
 They did not listen to the voice of
 the LORD.

26 Therefore He ^{1a}swore to them
 That He would cast them down in
 the wilderness,

27 And that He would ^acast their seed
 among the nations
 And ^bscatter them in the lands.

Psa. 106:28 They ^ajoined
 themselves also to ¹Baal-peor,
 And ate ^bsacrifices offered to the
 dead.

29 Thus they ^aprovoked *Him* to anger
 with their deeds,
 And the plague broke out among
 them.

30 Then Phinehas ^astood up and
 interposed,
 And so the ^bplague was stayed.

31 And it was ^areckoned to him for
 righteousness,

עֲצֻבֵיהֶם וַיִּהְיוּ לָהֶם לְמוֹקֵשׁ : 37
 וַיִּזְבְּחוּ אֶת־בְּנֵיהֶם וְאֶת־בְּנוֹתֵיהֶם
 לְשִׁדִּים : 38 וַיִּשְׁפְּכוּ דָם נָקִי דָם־
 בְּנֵיהֶם וּבְנוֹתֵיהֶם אֲשֶׁר זָבְחוּ
 לְעֲצֻבֵי כְנַעַן וַתַּחַנְךָ הָאָרֶץ
 בַּדָּמִים : 39 וַיִּטְמְאוּ בְּמַעֲשֵׂיהֶם וַיִּזְנוּ
 בְּמַעַל לְלִיְיָהֶם : 40 וַיִּחַר־אַף יְהוָה
 בְּעַמּוֹ וַיִּתְעַב אֶת־נַחֲלָתוֹ : 41 וַיִּתְנַם
 בְּיַד־גּוֹיִם וַיִּמְשְׁלוּ בָהֶם שְׂנֵאֵיהֶם :
 42 וַיִּלְחָצוּם אוֹיְבֵיהֶם וַיִּכְנְעוּ תַּחַת
 יָדָם : 43 פְּעָמִים רַבּוֹת יִצְּלֹם וְהִפְּה
 יִמְרוּ בַעֲצָתָם וַיִּמְכוּ בַעֲוֹנָם : 44
 וַיֵּרָא בַצָּר לָהֶם בְּשִׁמְעוֹ אֶת־
 רִנָּתָם : 45 וַיִּזְכֹּר לָהֶם בְּרִיתוֹ וַיִּנָּחֵם
 כָּל־בְּרִיתוֹ [תְּסַדְּרוּ] : 46 וַיִּתֵּן אוֹתָם
 לְרַחֲמִים לְפָנָי כָּל־שׁוֹבֵיהֶם : 47
 הוֹשִׁיעֵנו אִיְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ וְקַבְּצֵנוּ
 מִן־הַגּוֹיִם לְהַרְוֹת לְשָׁם קִדְשֶׁךָ
 לְהַשְׁתַּבַּח בְּתַהֲלֻתֶךָ : 48 בְּרוּךְ־
 יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל מִן־הָעוֹלָם |
 וְעַד הָעוֹלָם וְאָמַר כָּל־הָעַם אֲמֵן
 הִלְלוּ־יְיָ :

To all generations forever.

Psa. 106:32 They also ^aprovoked
Him to wrath at the waters of ¹Meribah,
So that it ^bwent hard with Moses
on their account;
³³ Because they ^awere rebellious
against ¹His Spirit,
He spoke rashly with his lips.

Psa. 106:34 They ^adid not destroy
the peoples,
As ^bthe LORD commanded them,
³⁵ But ^athey mingled with the nations
And learned their ¹practices,
³⁶ And ^aserved their idols,
^bWhich became a snare to them.
³⁷ They even ^asacrificed their sons
and their daughters to the ^bdemons,
³⁸ And shed ^ainnocent blood,
The blood of their ^bsons and their
daughters,
Whom they sacrificed to the idols
of Canaan;
And the land was ^cpolluted with
the blood.
³⁹ Thus they became ^aunclean in their
¹practices,
And ^bplayed the harlot in their
deeds.

Psa. 106:40 Therefore the ^aanger
of the LORD was kindled against His
people
And He ^babhorred His
^{1c}inheritance.
⁴¹ Then ^aHe gave them into the hand
of the ¹nations,
And those who hated them ruled
over them.

⁴² Their enemies also ^aoppressed them,

And they were subdued under their ¹power.

⁴³ Many times He would ^adeliver them;

They, however, were rebellious in their ^bcounsel,

And *so* ^csank down in their iniquity.

Psa. 106:44 Nevertheless He looked upon their distress

When He ^aheard their cry;

⁴⁵ And He ^aremembered His covenant for their sake,

And ^{1b}relented ^caccording to the greatness of His lovingkindness.

⁴⁶ He also made them ^aobjects of compassion

In the presence of all their captors.

Psa. 106:47 ^aSave us, O LORD our God,

And ^bgather us from among the nations,

To give thanks to Your holy name

And ^{1c}glory in Your praise.

⁴⁸ ^aBlessed be the LORD, the God of Israel,

From everlasting even to everlasting.

And let all the people say, "Amen."

¹Praise ²the LORD!

References

Psalm 106:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 105:1; 107:1; 118:1; 136:1; Jer 33:11

^b2 Chr 5:13; 7:3; Ezra 3:11; Ps 100:5

^c1 Chr 16:34, 41

Psalm 106:2

^aPs 145:4, 12; 150:2

Psalm 106:3

¹Or *judgment*

²Many Heb mss read *The one who performs*

^aPs 15:2

Psalm 106:4

¹Lit *of*

^aPs 44:3; 119:132

Psalm 106:5

¹I.e. people

^aPs 1:3

^bPs 118:15

^cPs 105:3

Psalm 106:6

¹Lit *with*

^a1 Kin 8:47; Ezra 9:7; Neh 1:7; Jer 3:25; Dan 9:5

^b2 Chr 30:7; Neh 9:2; Ps 78:8, 57; Zech 1:4

Psalm 106:7

¹I.e. wonderful acts

²Lit *the multitude of Your lovingkindnesses*

³Lit *Sea of Reeds*

^aJudg 3:7; Ps 78:11, 42

^bEx 14:11, 12; Ps 78:17

Psalm 106:8

^aEzek 20:9

^bEx 9:16

Psalm 106:9

¹Lit *Sea of Reeds*

^aPs 18:15; 78:13; Is 50:2; Nah 1:4

^bEx 14:21; Is 51:10

^cIs 63:11-13

Psalm 106:10

¹Or *power*

^aEx 14:30

^bPs 78:42; 107:2

Psalm 106:11

^aEx 14:27, 28; 15:5; Ps 78:53

Psalm 106:12

^aEx 14:31

^bEx 15:1-21; Ps 105:43

Psalm 106:13

^aEx 15:24; 16:2; 17:2

^bPs 107:11

Psalm 106:14

¹Or *put God to the test*

^aNum 11:4; Ps 78:18; 1 Cor 10:6

^bEx 17:2; 1 Cor 10:9

Psalm 106:15

¹Or *leanness into their soul*

^aNum 11:31; Ps 78:29

^bIs 10:16

Psalm 106:16

^aNum 16:1-3

Psalm 106:17

¹Or *assembly, band*

^aNum 16:32; Deut 11:6

Psalm 106:18

¹Or *assembly, band*

^aNum 16:35

Psalm 106:19

^aEx 32:4; Deut 9:8; Acts 7:41

Psalm 106:20

^aJer 2:11; Rom 1:23

Psalm 106:21

^aPs 78:11; 106:7, 13

^bDeut 10:21

Psalm 106:22

¹I.e. Wonderful acts

²Lit *Sea of Reeds*

^aPs 105:27

Psalm 106:23

^aEx 32:10; Deut 9:14; Ezek 20:8, 13

^bEx 32:11-14; Deut 9:25-29

Psalm 106:24

^aNum 14:31

^bDeut 8:7; Jer 3:19; Ezek 20:6

^cDeut 1:32; 9:23; Heb 3:19

Psalm 106:25

^aNum 14:2; Deut 1:27

Psalm 106:26

¹Lit *lifted up His hand*

^aNum 14:28-35; Ps 95:11; Ezek 20:15; Heb 3:11

Psalm 106:27

^aDeut 4:27

^bLev 26:33; Ps 44:11

Psalm 106:28

¹Or *Baal of Peor*

^aNum 25:3; Deut 4:3; Hos 9:10

^bNum 25:2

Psalm 106:29

^aNum 25:4

Psalm 106:30

^aNum 25:7

^bNum 25:8

Psalm 106:31

^aGen 15:6; Num 25:11-13

Psalm 106:32

¹Lit *strife*

^aNum 20:2-13; Ps 81:7; 95:9

^bNum 20:12

Psalm 106:33

¹Or *his spirit*

^aNum 20:3, 10; Ps 78:40; 107:11

Psalm 106:34

^aJudg 1:21, 27-36

^bDeut 7:2, 16

Psalm 106:35

¹Lit *works*

^aJudg 3:5, 6

Psalm 106:36

^aJudg 2:12

^bDeut 7:16

Psalm 106:37

^aDeut 12:31; 32:17; 2 Kin 16:3; 17:17; Ezek 16:20, 21; 1 Cor 10:20

^bLev 17:7

Psalm 106:38

^aPs 94:21

^bDeut 18:10
^cNum 35:33; Is 24:5; Jer 3:1, 2

Psalm 106:39

¹Lit *works*
^aLev 18:24; Ezek 20:18
^bLev 17:7; Num 15:39; Judg 2:17; Hos 4:12

Psalm 106:40

¹I.e. people
^aJudg 2:14; Ps 78:59
^bLev 26:30; Deut 32:19
^cDeut 9:29; 32:9

Psalm 106:41

¹Or *Gentiles*
^aJudg 2:14; Neh 9:27

Psalm 106:42

¹Lit *hand*
^aJudg 4:3; 10:12

Psalm 106:43

^aJudg 2:16-18
^bPs 81:12
^cJudg 6:6

Psalm 106:44

^aJudg 3:9; 6:7; 10:10

Psalm 106:45

¹Lit *was sorry*
^aLev 26:42; Ps 105:8
^bJudg 2:18
^cPs 69:16

Psalm 106:46

^{a1} Kin 8:50; 2 Chr 30:9; Ezra 9:9; Neh 1:11; Jer 42:12

Psalm 106:47

¹Lit *boast*

^a1 Chr 16:35, 36

^bPs 147:2

^cPs 47:1

Psalm 106:48

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^cPs 41:13; 72:18; 89:52

Targum

Psa. 106:1 Hallelujah! Give thanks in the presence of the LORD, for he is good, for his goodness is forever. ² Who is able to utter the might of the LORD? [Who] is allowed to proclaim all his praises? ³ Happy are they who observe judgment, those who do righteousness at every time. ⁴ Remember me, O LORD, with good will toward your people; call me to mind with your redemption. ⁵ To look on the plenty of your chosen ones; to rejoice in the joy of your people; to join in praise with your inheritance. ⁶ We have sinned, along with our fathers; we have committed iniquity, acted wickedly. ⁷ Our fathers in Egypt paid no heed to your wonders; they did not call to mind your great goodness; and they rebelled against your word by the sea, at the Sea of Reeds. ⁸ And he redeemed them for his name's sake, to make known his might. ⁹ And he rebuked the Sea of Reeds, and it dried up; and he conducted them through the deeps, as in the wilderness. ¹⁰ And he redeemed them from the power of the foe; and he redeemed them from the power of the enemies. ¹¹ And the waters covered their oppressors; not one of them was left. ¹² And they believed in the name of his word; they sang his praise. ¹³ They quickly forgot his deeds; they did not wait for his counsel. ¹⁴ And they made a request and tested God in the place of desolation. ¹⁵ And he gave them their request, and sent leanness into their souls. ¹⁶ And they were jealous of Moses in the camp, of Aaron, the holy one of the LORD. ¹⁷ The earth opened up and swallowed Dathan, and covered the company of Abiram. ¹⁸ And fire burned in their company; flame will kindle the wicked. ¹⁹ They made a calf in Horeb, and bowed down to something of metal. ²⁰ And they exchanged the glory of their master for the likeness of a bull that eats grass and befouls itself. ²¹ They forgot God their redeemer who had done mighty works in Egypt. ²² Wonders in the land of Ham, awesome things by the Sea of Reeds. ²³ And he commanded by his word to destroy them, had it not been for Moses his chosen one, who stood and grew mighty in prayer in his presence to turn aside his wrath from obliteration. ²⁴ And their soul was repelled by the desirable land; they did not believe his word. ²⁵ And they complained in their tents; they did not accept the word of the LORD. ²⁶ And he lifted his hand in an oath because of them, to throw them down slain in the wilderness. ²⁷ And to exile their seed among the peoples, and to scatter them among the lands. ²⁸ And they attached themselves to the idol of Peor, and they ate the sacrifices of the dead. ²⁹ And they caused anger in his presence by their deeds, and plague attacked them. ³⁰ And Phinehas rose and prayed, and the plague was restrained. ³¹ And it was accounted to him for merit for all generations forever. ³² And they caused anger by the waters of Dispute, and it grieved Moses because of them. ³³ For they rebelled against his holy spirit, and he had explained [it] clearly with his lips. ³⁴ They did not destroy the peoples, which the LORD had commanded them [to do]. ³⁵ And they mingled with the Gentiles and they learned their deeds. ³⁶ And they worshipped their idol, and they became a stumbling-block for them. ³⁷ And they sacrificed their sons and their daughters to the demons. ³⁸ And they shed innocent blood – the blood of their

sons and daughters that they sacrificed to the idols of the Canaanites – and the land was defiled by capital crimes. ³⁹ And brought uncleanness by their deeds and went astray by their acts. ⁴⁰ And the anger of the LORD was harsh against his people and he despised his inheritance. ⁴¹ And he handed them over into the power of the Gentiles, and their foes ruled over them. ⁴² And their enemies oppressed them, and they were subdued under their hand. ⁴³ Many times he would deliver them, but they would rebel against him in their counsel, and they were brought low in their sins. ⁴⁴ And he saw when it went ill with them, when he heard their prayer. ⁴⁵ And he remembered his covenant in their favor, and he turned aside from his anger according to his abundant mercies. ⁴⁶ And he made them find mercy in the sight of all who had taken them captive. ⁴⁷ Redeem us, O LORD our God, and gather us from among the Gentiles, to give thanks in your holy name, to boast in your praise. ⁴⁸ Blessed be the name of the LORD God of Israel, from this age to the age to come, and let all the people say, Amen, Hallelujah.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm continues the narrative from Psalm 105. The Psalmist wrote about how the LORD sustained the Jews as they wandered in the wilderness for forty years. While the LORD displayed his unprecedented kindness to Israel, the people neglected their duty to the LORD. They rebelled against Moses and Aaron, which initiated their moral and ethical decline, eventually leading to the Babylonian Exile.

Verse four

Every person must remember that they are responsible for their duties to the LORD. One's loyalty must always be to the LORD. In addition, they must remember that they are a Jewish community member.

Remember me, O LORD, in the favor You extend to Your people; O think of me at Your salvation.

Notes on the Psalm

Taking the LORD for granted happened in Israel's past and still happens today. One of the obligations is to serve the LORD in some capacity. In the Christian Scriptures, Saint Paul wrote that every person contributes some God-given talent to the community. The same holds true in the Hebrew Scriptures. Every member of the community contributes something unique to the person. Part of the covenant with the LORD is to study the Scriptures. Clearly, today this is not an imperative in most communities. Whether it is the synagogue or church, the attendance and participation of people are declining rapidly. US society has been under pressure to remove God from all aspects of life, and the woke have become very good at it. Part of their success is that people who say they are God-fearing really are not. They are not reading and studying their Bible. They are not attending synagogues and church worship events.

Apathy has invaded religious life in the US and this is destroying God worship. During the Covid pandemic political leaders had no problem shutting down churches. Even church bishops begged churches to shutdown. This exasperated the problem causing even more decline. Apathy can set in quickly once the “habit” of attending worship celebrations is broken. The motto “in God we trust” which is on US currency will probably be attacked next and the woke might win. How can God serving people fight back when their numbers are so small.

Eventually the LORD will intervene into our society. The LORD sent the Babylonians to Jerusalem to destroy the Temple because it was not being used for its proper purpose. Different cults were celebrating in the Temple. The LORD had no choice but to remove His house from the earth. How long will the LORD watch what is happening here? The best thing for people to do is to reverse the downward trend in morality that is taking over society. Ask yourself what you can do.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

